

Digital Design Techniques for Adaptable Systems: Prague Biennale Pavilion

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ABSTRACT

Based upon a completed practice-based research project, this paper presents information on the design process and computational methods used to develop advanced adaptive geometries in relationship to behavioural goals, criteria and constraints. The paper highlights potential strengths of the approach, draws attention to foundational theoretical considerations and provides a basis for future work.

Keywords: Situated performance, parametric architectural design, new media art

INTRODUCTION

The International Biennale of Contemporary Arts, The Second Sight, was organised and run in the city of Prague by the Czech National Gallery. This large-scale international event continued from 13 June until 11 September, 2005. The Performative Space section of the Biennale included an experimental location-and-practice-based research project that was developed in the Cambridge University Moving Image Studio and the Digital Studio of the Department of Architecture.

Fig. 1. [A] Fragment of the locally variable Voronoi-cell structure conforming to the shape of the dynamic surface (digital rendering). [B] The outer shell in construction on site (photograph). <1> Disused lift shaft. <2> Video projectors.

¹ The first two names are in alphabetical order.

The design process consisted of three parts. The first part, which is the primary concern of this paper, used digital dynamic simulation to produce two organic shells fitting into an existing stairwell space (Fig. 2). The second part dealt with the design of the computer-driven responsive audio-visual system. The third part used the two shells output of part one and developed them into building components taking into account the performative requirements of the audio-visual system.

Fig. 2. Side view of the structure with the lift shaft removed. (digital rendering)

PERFORMATIVE SITUATIONS

Fundamental to the project is a theoretical perspective that understands architectural environments as time-bound performative situations that are made up of social, practical and motivational involvements. One of the project's ambitions was to establish a workflow that could lead to synergy between traditional architectural concerns and the situations of direct engagement as developed by performance practitioners, game players or, recently, by new media artists; see (Imperiale, 2002) or (Oosterhuis, 2003) for the background discussion from the architectural perspective. Two primary tensions were considered as the formative forces for design: access through bodily movement and visual access. In short, when these types of access are disturbed in a location that already sustains a complex life, new social encounters must ensue. Similar concepts have been explored by architects experimenting with "sensory spaces" such as the ADA Space project (Eng, 2004). The Prague Biennale project impacted on the two types of access by installing a built structure (Fig. 7), projecting moving images through space upon surfaces and people (Fig. 3) and creating a soundscape. The sound and images were remixed in real time in response to human behaviour as observed by the computer-vision system.

The goal was not to create a "beautiful" object but to set up conditions for the emergence of meaning. For example, the audio-visual field of the installation would come to life only with the arrival of people who cast shadows, moved through the structures, assumed and shed social stances. The installation did not have a meaning by itself, as a structure devoid of people. Rather, its meanings emerged as a story of tensions: between the perfect completeness of the digital and the untidy of the physical, between

ambitious concepts and practical constraints, between goals seen as the desire to make objects and goals seen as playful exploration that is meaningful in its own right. The work on this project strived to develop and test the techniques that could help to erode the boundary between the digital and the physical by establishing multi-modal and open-ended design processes able to accept and guide imagination and respond to inputs normally left outside of the architectural domain.

Fig. 3. [A] The effect produced by the responsive audio-visual system. Moving images were projected onto the structure and through the structure onto the walls so that image patterns and shadows merged into a continuous field able to integrate bodily movement. [B] Emergent reflections and refractions were colorized purple and green due to the polarizing effect of the transparent-plastic cell-skins. The colour depended on the orientation of the cell-skin in relationship to the projector beam. (photographs)

SOFTWARE ENVIRONMENTS

The design required an integrated development environment able to support complex geometries, advanced animation including dynamic simulation and flexible automation tools. Based on these requirements, Alias Maya was selected for the task. MEL-based automation routines were developed in support of form-finding techniques capable of supporting versioning and prototype breeding. Other stages of the design relied on such programmable environments as Rhino 3D and MAX/MSP/Jitter.

FORM-FINDING

The design of flexible architectures via time- and motion-based techniques has been developed and discussed by several practitioners including Lynn (1999), OCEAN-NORTH (2005) and C. Williams (Leach et al., 2004). The approach described in this paper followed the basic principles established for the improvisational mode of designing where suitable topologies are acted upon by a multitude of forces. The Prague Biennale project relied on this emerging methodology and contributed theoretical and technical insights to its application in practice. From the very beginning the project was envisaged not as an object or even a place but as a performative situation that included design, construction, exhibition and dissemination stages. All of these stages provided versatile opportunities for direct involvement and learning for various groups of participants not normally classed as a valid audience for an exhibition piece. This perspective led to fundamental re-evaluation of criteria for design development and assessment. A detailed discussion of architectural projects as performative situations is beyond the scope of this paper but will be developed in further work. This paper instead describes the practical implementation of a flexible and modular design work-

flow that explored the use of dynamic curves for holistic dynamic-surface control – a technique that, to the knowledge of the authors, has never been used before.

At each stage of the process, a particular intermediate version - the “surviving design” – had to be chosen among a series of options produced by aleatory or time-based processes. The surviving designs were selected according to multiple criteria: those formulated by the designers in response to the practice-based research processes and those dictated by the logic of physical construction. The influences on choices were both intuitive (form, proportions, imagined impact) and analytical (production requirements, construction technique, time, finances, logistics, formal novelty, potential for further research and development).

Establishment: Guiding Planes

The designers manually created the guiding planes: two pairs, top and bottom, for the outer shell (Fig. 7 <2>) and two pairs for the inner shell (Fig. 7 <3>). The planes were made by lofting a degree-1 NURBS surface along a set of four NURBS curves (Fig. 7 <7>). The planes were lofted clockwise and their origins aligned towards one corner of the stairwell. Geometrically, the planes were modelled to trace the outlines of the stairwell walls and the disused lift shaft in the centre of the space. Their vertical positions were aligned to the horizontal plane of the ceiling at the top and the slope of the steps at the bottom. The position of the planes guided the top and bottom rims of the respected shells while their width controlled the amount of shell-surface deviation.

Exploration: Dynamic Curves and Surfaces

Working with one pair of planes at a time, the designers performed the next operation that was represented as one step but consisted of several procedures run as one unit of code. The script was loaded from a Maya-interface shelf and presented its options via a custom-built GUI. The options included: 1) the number of guiding curves to distribute; 2) whether the curve-end points were to be sorted along U or V; 3) the value for dynamic-curve sample density; 4) whether the dynamic surface was to be periodic or non-periodic; and 5) point lock type – whether the ends of the curve were to be fixed in space or free to move.

The script distributed two sets of points, one for each of the two guiding planes. The points were distributed randomly in the UV space of their respective guiding planes. After the initial distribution, the points were left random in the U direction but were sorted in descending order along V. This sorting ensured that the resulting dynamic surface was free of overlaps that would render it unsuitable for the cell-based construction workflow. The points were also sorted into arrays in the order of their creation. The distribution of points is a primary formative operation and can be related to the samples of data collected on-site or derived via a simulation.

Fig. 4. Design variations, part one. [A] and [B] shared all settings; the difference in form was due to the randomization of curve-end positions. In [C], the curve-end points were sorted along U rather than along V while the other values were the same with [A] and [B]. The red dashed line shows the dominant vertical direction the surface assumed if curve-ends were sorted in V. Sorting along U produced self-intersecting geometry and self-intersecting solutions, which, while interesting in their own right, were avoided in this project as unsuitable for the chosen construction process. <1> Top guiding plane. <2> Bottom guiding plane. <3> Surface isoparms. <4> Self-intersecting geometry. (screen captures)

Fig. 5. Design variations, part two. [A] and [B] were generated under the same settings except from the number of dynamic curves that was 4 for [A] and 30 for [B]. Higher numbers of curves produced surfaces that tended to follow more closely the shape of the guiding planes and had higher probability for self-intersection. [C] Dynamic curves distributed between guiding planes. <1> A small scale detail and an area of possible self-intersection. <2> Dynamic curve. (screen captures)

Next, a NURBS curve was drawn between each pair of corresponding points in the two arrays. Each of the curves was converted into a dynamic hair and the attributes of each follicle were set according to the designer's input. The same number of dynamic curves – seven – were used to build and guide both the outer and the inner shells (Fig. 7). Multiple distributions with various settings were created (Figs. 4, 5).

The exploratory nature of the design process suggested that the digital tools used for form-finding should not constrain the outcome too rigidly because unpredictable configurations were valued as the foundation of serendipity and non-standard solutions. The same experimentation demonstrated that very loosely constrained geometries should also be avoided because they tended to produce results that were difficult or impossible to analyse, classify and build.

The dynamic surface versions generated using seven curves provided a rich selection of surprising yet controlled geometries. Lower numbers tended to produce a simplistic form that often deviated dramatically from the shape of the guiding planes. Higher numbers produced geometry that followed the guiding planes too directly while also introducing areas with extreme curvature and overlaps (Fig. 5 [B]).

Fig. 6. An alternative design solution. The relationship between guiding planes, dynamic curves and a dynamic surface is shown at three different stages of the process. [A] Curves and surface after distribution, frame 0. [B] Frame 362. [C] Frame 603. <1> Guiding planes. <2> Curves responding to dynamic forces. <3> Top guiding plane followed the outer wall of the stairwell. <4> Bottom guiding plane wrapped around the disused lift shaft. <5>-<8> Curves belonging to one hair system: Drag 0.250, Dump 0, Friction 0.5, Mass 1, Gravity 0, Turbulence Intensity 0.1, Turbulence Frequency 0.2, Turbulence Speed 0.2. (screen captures)

Another important parameter that defines the behaviour of a dynamic curve and the dynamic surface that it guides is sample density. The default factor of two doubles the number of curve CVs and makes the curve more flexible and, in conjunction with other settings, less stiff. Initially, the curves were created as degree 1 curves with 4 CVs. The dynamic curves were then set to have sample density of 3 and degree 3 so that each curve had 12 CVs.

These settings had a direct impact on the form and behaviour of the dynamic surface that was produced by lofting the curves into a surface. This operation created a topologically cylindrical surface whose movement was controlled by the movement of the dynamic curves. The tubular nature of the dynamic surface was predetermined by the topology of the guiding planes and the designer's instruction for the script to create a periodic surface. Two surfaces, inner and outer, were created, each governed by a corresponding guiding plane. In Maya, when a curve is made dynamic it is associated with a hair system. Many curves can be governed by one such system. If these curves are used to make a lofted surface, the procedural relationship is preserved and the deformations of the lofted surface are driven by the associated hair system. The surviving design used two hair systems – one for each surface (Fig. 9 [B]).

The dynamic-curve ends can be left loose or locked at their initial positions and this setting can lead to dramatically different results. Four settings are possible: no lock, tip lock, base lock and both-ends lock. Experiments with all four attachments were conducted and the no-lock type was used for the surviving design.

Fig. 7. [A] The surviving design components at frame 0. [B] Guiding planes of the outer dynamic surface and curves. <1> Outer dynamic surface with twenty-one U spans and seven V spans. <2> Guiding planes and seven curves of the outer surface. <3> Guiding planes and seven curves of the inner surface. <4> Inner dynamic surface with twenty-five U spans and seven V spans. <5> Profile curve used in the guiding-plane loft. <6> Direction of loft. <7> Guiding-plane loft. <8> Dynamic curve.

Fig. 8. Refinement with fields. Structural solutions. [A] Deformation of a test surface under the influence of three spherical volume axis fields. [B] Alternative design that considered the position and direction of the projector beams. The positions of the projectors were driven by the deforming geometry. [C] Alternative design and construction method using horizontal and vertical ribs. <1> Dynamic surface. <2> Projectors. <3> Dynamic surface. <4> Structural elements. (screen captures)

The procedure was automated into a complete cycle that did not require manual interference once initiated yet could be readjusted in a number of ways. The most significant controls were presented as easy-to-adjust custom-built GUI. Automation and introduction of randomness allowed rapid iterative experimentation with form where the parameters for all settings were established via multiple iterations. It also supported in the digital domain a heuristic form-finding fuzzy-feedback routine similar to that traditionally sustained by such techniques as thumbnail sketching.

Procedural automation for form-finding as developed by the project can serve as a foundation for a flexible system with multiple input points able to accept data from other parts of the system, on-site observations or AI-driven simulations.

Fig. 9. Inner and outer shells as the product of several intermediate surviving-design solutions. [A] Dynamic surfaces in the stairwell (frame 0). [B] Dynamic curves in the initial position and lines showing the flows of movement through the space. [C] Dynamic surfaces in the surviving position (frame 180). [D] Force-fields and the outer dynamic surface in the initial state. Circles represent radial fields and triangles represent uniform fields. Outer surface fields are red and inner surface fields are white. The figures next to the fields show Magnitude, Attenuation and Maximum Distance. [F] Plan views of the dynamic surfaces in the initial (frame 0) and the final state (frame 180). <1> Outer dynamic surface. <2> Inner dynamic surface. <3> Entrance to the stairwell from the Main Hall of the museum. <4> Entry from the secondary street entrance that also served as the main entrance during the evening shows. <5> Path to the Performative Space section of the exhibition. <6> Two sets of dynamic curves. (screen captures)

Refinement: Fields and Particles

After the dynamic surfaces were ready, they were deformed into shape with dynamic force-fields and partially controlled turbulence affecting the hair systems (Fig. 8 [A]). The surviving version used eleven radial fields and two uniform fields (Fig. 9 [D]). The capabilities of the dynamic surfaces were explored via multiple iterations and the results adjusted to fit a number of constraints on lines of passage, visibility, degrees of curvature and surface continuity. The surviving version was the state of the model at frame 180 (Fig. 9 [C]).

The control via force-fields provided a flexible cumulative method of influencing the evolution of the surfaces. In addition to its usefulness in surface manipulation, this

approach opens additional entry points for data input and allows holistic deformation of several interlinked components. For example, we have experimented with deformations of the visual field as defined by the placement and orientation of the projectors (Fig 8 [C]).

Fig. 10. Refinement with fields and particles. [A] Surfaces before refinement. Red circles show the areas that did not comply with the criteria as specified by the designers and dictated by the needs of construction. [B] Refined surfaces. [C] The diagram of the dynamic surface converted into a soft body. <1> and <2> Areas where the dynamic surface intersected the bounding walls of the stairwell. <3> Bird's eye perspective showing a problem area. <4> Plan view. <5> Rigid bodies used to push the dynamic surface into the confines of the stairwell. <6> and <7> Animated rigid bodies. <8> The offset from ground was low to provoke a direct behavioural response from the visitors and passers-by. <9> The offset between two surfaces was too small to accommodate the width of the construction elements and had to be adjusted.

After the basic shape of each surface was established using dynamic fields, the surface was converted into a soft body. Four rectangular passive rigid bodies were then created to correspond to the four walls of the stairwell enclosure (Fig. 10 [C]). These were animated to push the surfaces into the confines of the stairwell. This procedure

produced another kind of surface articulation in response to the local requirements that was impossible to achieve with dynamic curves (Fig. 10 [B]). The particles that govern the deformations of a soft body were distributed much more densely and uniformly than the curves and provided a way to control the surface in relationship to the existing geometry without manual manipulation.

PRODUCTION AND CONSTRUCTION

In parallel with the modelling, experiments were undertaken to develop and test the production of components using computer-controlled machinery as part of the unified digital fabrication workflow. These experiments were formulated by the design process and were informing the design process at the same time. Construction workflow was developed in parallel, taking into account the logistics issues that were made apparent during the construction of a 1:10 model.

A detailed description of the building-element production and the construction workflow is outside the scope of this paper. In short, the dynamic surfaces were materialised with cell-like construction elements whose form was determined by adaptable Voronoi-based patterns (Fig. 1 <1>). A project by Wingate (2005) is a precedent for the use of 2D Voronoi tiles to produce decorative/structural cells on a flat surface; our paper describes the first use of 2D Voronoi tiles to establish the form of structural cells that follow a free-form surface (Fig. 1 [A]).

The Prague Biennale project developed an automated workflow where cell-walls and cell-skins were generated, unfolded and labelled automatically with the use of specifically written scripts produced in collaboration with A. Kudless. Cell-walls were cut out of cardboard by a computer-controlled laser cutter. Kiechle (2004) and Kudless (2005) discuss a range of related cardboard-based techniques. A transparent plastic skin was attached to each folded cell-wall to form a cell. The cells were assembled into patches that were suspended in the stairwell and connected together to form the shells (Fig. 3 [B]).

CONCLUSION

The workflow succeeded in producing complex buildable surfaces using a series of layered procedural relationships. Such a workflow can be seen as a backbone of the simulative form-finding process that can be informed by various types of input, inter-operating in a non-destructive and flexible fashion. A pluralistic and responsive approach to design is well-suited for designing interactive and responsive environments. Digital data, in the form of samples, relationships or procedures is a foundation for the design techniques that span the boundaries of established professional fields. The future work will take the design workflow as developed for this project and seek to elaborate on its achievements by arranging for more intelligent constraints and input. This intelligence can come from digital simulation, AI routines, on-site measurements, computer-awareness systems and the like, while the design results can be incorporated in computationally augmented, structurally mobile environments that can direct and interpret human relationships with novel dramatic and narrative consequences.

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